

Open Research Data: SNSF monitoring report 2017-2018

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Abstract

The Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) introduced its policy on Open Research Data (ORD) in 2017. This monitoring report gives an overview of the first experiences and provides an analysis of the adherence of researchers to the ORD policy. Data collected in this report come from the applications funded in the project funding scheme, some career funding schemes, and the Sinergia programme between October 2017 and December 2018. The report provides an analysis of the plausibility of the data management plans (DMPs), the requested costs for granting access to research data and the characteristics of the mentioned data repositories.

Keywords: Open Research Data, Data Management Plan, Data sharing, Data repositories, Science Policy.

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1 Introduction

The Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) introduced its policy on Open Research Data (ORD) in 2017. This monitoring report gives an overview of the first experiences and provides an analysis of the adherence of researchers to the ORD policy. The main topics discussed in this document are the core principles of the ORD policy, the requested costs for granting access to research data, the plausibility of the Data Management Plans (DMPs) submitted to the SNSF, and the characteristics of the mentioned data repositories.

Managing and sharing research data as openly as possible is one of the principles of good scientific practice. The SNSF adheres to this principle, as stated in the article 47 of its Funding Regulations “[...] *data collected with the aid of an SNSF grant must also be made available to other researchers for further research and integrated into recognised scientific data pools*”. Additionally, in 2017 the SNSF published a policy on ORD in order to define in greater detail its position on this important subject, the main principle being that research data sharing makes a fundamental contribution to the impact, transparency and reproducibility of scientific research. The aim is to encourage re-use of data in order to enhance the quality and efficiency of research and to enable new research.

In order to implement the ORD policy, the SNSF introduced the DMP in most of its funding schemes. The aim of the DMP is to encourage researchers to reflect on research data management and data sharing from the start of their project. Additionally, the SNSF is aware that the preparation of data and the data upload itself may take time and require financial resources. These costs are covered by the SNSF (in general up to a maximum of CHF 10,000). Furthermore, the Scientific Exchanges funding scheme supports the events that focus on Open Research Data, where research communities can discuss and define best practices for their disciplines.

This analysis is meant to provide feedback to different stakeholders involved in ORD discussions, to the Swiss research community as well as the research institutions that were directly affected by the ORD policy and put in place support structures and guidance. Moreover, the SNSF visited many institutions before, during and after the implementation of the policy to make its expectations clear and to discuss the needs and worries of the researchers. Additionally, it regularly publishes news about this topic on its website. The results concerning the DMPs will allow the SNSF to assess whether the communication measures have been useful and well-received by the applicants.

This document is based on the “intentions” declared by the applicants in their DMP at the proposal submission stage. An analysis of the actual data sharing and management practices of the researchers will only be possible in 2-3 years, once enough projects have been completed and the final versions of the DMPs are available. This will be the object of a future, more comprehensive monitoring report.

The SNSF ORD policy is not an isolated effort but an initiative well aligned with recent developments in the field of ORD at the international level (ERC, UK Concordat on Open Research Data, FWF, DFG, NIH, ANR), as well as with two sets of recommendations proposed by Science Europe (Science Europe, 2019) concerning the international alignment in data management practices.

2 ORD Policy and Processes

2.1 ORD Policy

2.1.1 Core Principles

The SNSF ORD policy is based on core principles related to research data management. More precisely, the SNSF expects all researchers with SNSF grants to:

- store the research data they have worked on and produced during the course of their research work,
- share these data with other researchers, unless they are bound by legal, ethical, copyright, confidentiality or other clauses, and

- deposit their data and metadata onto existing public repositories in formats that anyone can find, access and reuse without restriction.

Data should be shared as soon as possible, but at the latest together with the relevant scientific publication, meaning that the data should be made available with the original publication and cannot be subjected to any embargo periods related to the open access publication following the “green road”.

Data can be raw or processed, depending on the project and the discipline. Datasets must always be carefully documented with associated metadata, such that other researchers understand how the data was collected, as well as under which conditions and how it can be re-used. If specific tools are needed to re-use the data, this needs to be documented and, if possible, the tools made available. In any case, the provided data and documentation (metadata) must be sufficient to ensure their reusability. Researchers are asked to explain in their DMP whenever these requirements cannot be met.

2.1.2 FAIR Data Principles

To facilitate the discovery, access, re-use and citation of datasets, it is important that the publication of research data follows a set of clearly defined and broadly applicable best practices. The FAIR Data Principles define a range of qualities a published dataset should have in order to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (see the explanation of the FAIR Data Principles).

The SNSF expects researchers to share their data according to the FAIR Data Principles on publicly accessible, digital repositories. It is important to note that the FAIR Data Principles do not require researchers to share all their data without any restrictions. Rather, they advocate applying a standard procedure when sharing research data for reuse, so that humans and computer systems can easily find, interpret and use them under clearly defined conditions. To make the transition towards FAIR research data easier, the SNSF decided to fix a set of minimal criteria that repositories have to fulfil:

- Globally unique and persistent identifiers are attributed to data sets (e.g. DOI)
- Upload of intrinsic (e.g. author’s name, content of dataset, associated publication, etc.) and submitter-defined (e.g. definition of variable names, etc.) metadata possible
- Reuse defined (e.g. Creative Commons, Open Data Commons, etc.)
- Citation information and metadata always (even in the case of datasets with restricted access) publicly accessible
- Intrinsic metadata submitted via standardized template/mask (to ensure machine readability and interoperability)
- Long-term preservation plan for the archived data in place

2.2 Processes

2.2.1 Costs for Granting Access to Research Data

In connection with the implementation of the ORD policy, the SNSF adapted on 1 April 2017 the article 2.13 of the General implementation regulations for the Funding Regulations in order to define the eligible costs for granting access to research data.

When submitting their application, researchers can budget ORD-related costs (the maximum charge per grant is generally CHF 10,000). The budget is intended to cover data preparation (prior to and for upload exclusively) and data archiving costs. The data preparation costs are for example intended to cover personnel costs, on a mandate basis, to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (data cleaning, preparation of metadata, etc.). Data archiving costs are covered by the SNSF if the data repository meets the FAIR Data Principles and does not serve any commercial purpose. Additionally, the SNSF contributes to these costs only on the basis of a single payment when the data are submitted to the data repository, in the sense of a Data Publishing Charge (see for example Dryad). Any subsequent costs are not covered by the SNSF.

2.2.2 Assessment of the DMP

The plausibility of the DMP and its compliance with the ORD requirements is assessed by the Administrative Offices of the SNSF. It is important to specify that DMPs are not part of the scientific evaluation process but that a plausible DMP is a condition for the release of funds. If there are any shortcomings in the DMP, especially related to the requirements defined in the ORD policy, the DMP will need to be revised. The DMP remains editable during the entire lifetime of the grant and its contents can be adapted as the project evolves. The definitive DMP must be provided by the end of the project at the latest, together with the financial and scientific reports of the project. The links to the datasets have to be indicated in the output data and will be available on the SNSF public database P3.

The Administrative Offices adopted a pragmatic approach for the assessment of DMPs: only issues concerning data sharing requirements were considered as potential reasons for revision. Other issues - e.g. lack of details about data collection or no indication of the definitive data repository - were subject to comments for the attention of the applicants, and have to be resolved at the latest by the end of the project grant, when the applicants are requested to submit their final version of the DMP.

3 Data

It is important to note that only data from approved applications were considered in this report, given that the SNSF does not assess the DMPs of rejected applications. Data collected in this report (N=1,516) come from the applications funded in the project funding scheme (October 2017, April 2018, October 2018; N=1,270), career funding scheme (PRIMA 2017, Eccellenza 2018, Ambizione November 2017, Doc.CH September 2018; N=188), and the Sinergia programme (December 2017, June 2018, December 2018; N=58).

The descriptive analysis presented in this report was prepared as follows:

- Costs budgeted for granting access to research data at the submission of the grant application extracted from the corresponding section on mySNF (“costs for granting access to research data (Open Research Data)”);
- Information related to data repositories extracted from the DMPs;
- Results of the DMPs’ assessment by the SNSF Administrative Offices.

The dataset used for this monitoring report is available on Zenodo (<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3618209>)

4 Descriptive Analysis

4.1 Costs for Granting Access to Research Data

Only a small proportion of applicants requests costs for granting access to research data (see Figure 1). Out of the 1,516 applications, 16% requested ORD costs. The remaining 84% did not budget ORD costs at the time of the submission or incidentally requested such costs under a different budget category. Of the 246 applications that budgeted ORD costs, the requested amount was most often in the CHF 5,000-10,000 range, followed by CHF 0-5,000, with 130 and 64 applications, respectively. In total, 52 applications budgeted more than CHF 10,000.

In order to have a better estimate of the annual budget for ORD costs at the SNSF, an additional analysis was prepared by considering all the SNSF calls with a mandatory DMP in 2018. This represents 33 calls and 1,257 approved applications. The total amount requested for granting access to research data in 2018 amounts to CHF 1,973,820, which corresponds to 0.2% of the total amount requested of CHF 989 Mio. However, it is important to emphasize that the requested CHF 2 Mio for ORD costs is indicative and subject to the following limitations:

- Some amounts indicated in the grant applications are mentioned without detailed justification and therefore do not allow an in-depth analysis of the eligibility of the costs. In these cases, the SNSF gave the researchers the benefit of the doubt and accepted these costs;

Figure 1: Budgeted ORD costs in the funded applications, all funding schemes (N=1,516)

- Some of the costs are not eligible. They were left in the budget, despite an incorrect interpretation of the regulations by the researchers, with the aim to support future ORD efforts in the individual projects. This was emphasized with a condition in the decision that the funds can only be used for data preparation and data archiving in a data repository that complies with the FAIR Data Principles and does not serve any commercial purpose;
- Some costs related to open research data are indicated in different budget categories and are therefore not accounted for;
- Some researchers did not request ORD costs because they might not be aware of the eligibility of these costs.

4.2 Overall Assessment of the DMPs

The assessment of the DMPs by the Administrative Offices produced three outcomes: the categories “accepted”, “conditionally accepted” and “revision”. Their meaning is as follows:

- DMP with status “accepted”: each sub-question of the DMP is well-addressed. Implicitly, these DMPs are not subject to major modifications at a later stage unless the applicants need to adapt them due to unforeseen changes to the planned research project;
- DMP with status “conditionally accepted”: the DMP is overall well documented and respects the ORD requirements. However, minor issues or shortcomings are present in certain sub-sections of the DMP, which have to be adapted or completed for the final version of the DMP (at the end of the project grant).
- DMP with status “revision”: some aspects of the DMP do not comply with the ORD requirements in terms of data sharing requirements. The DMP has to be revised before the release of funds.

Figure 2 presents the results of the assessment of the DMPs, overall and by main groups of disciplines (SSH: Social Sciences and Humanities, MINT: Mathematics, Information Sciences, Natural Sciences, and Technology, LS: Life Sciences). The Sinergia applications were not considered in this last analysis, as this instrument is designed for interdisciplinary projects. In total, 605 DMPs were accepted, 497 were conditionally accepted and 414 were sent back for revision. Therefore, 73% of the DMPs analysed do not conflict with the SNSF ORD requirements. The proportions in the three main groups of disciplines do not differ considerably, especially regarding the percentage of DMPs that were sent back for revision.

4.3 Detailed Assessment of the DMPs

This section provides a more detailed overview of the DMP’ assessment by presenting the main reasons why a DMP is conditionally accepted or considered to be in need of revision by the SNSF Administrative Offices.

Figure 2: Assessment of DMPs, all funding schemes and by group of disciplines (Overall N=1,516, SSH N=422, MINT N=513, LS N=523)

Figure 3 shows that many DMPs are accepted subject to certain conditions, especially due to the lack of information about the (final) choice of the data repository. In such cases, the *FAIRness* of the data repository cannot be assessed by the SNSF. The first category (“No repository [clearly] indicated”) includes the following cases:

- The applicants state that they will deposit their data in a data repository compliant with the FAIR data principles but no repository is explicitly mentioned;
- A (general) data repository is indicated as a fallback solution but the applicants mention that they might share their data elsewhere, in the event that discipline-specific initiatives will be operational at the end of the project grant;
- The applicants indicate that the choice of the data repository will depend on the data policy of the scientific journal in which they publish.

The second category (“Minor issues in the DMP form”) refers to the DMPs where the applicants’ explanations in the DMP form are insufficient but which nevertheless comply with the SNSF ORD policy.

The third category (“Not FAIR repository”) corresponds to the DMPs where the data repository indicated is not (yet) compliant with the FAIR Data Principles. It means that one or more SNSF requirements are not met or that the data repository is not yet operational. It also includes data repositories that do not provide sufficient information to be clearly verified as compliant with the SNSF criteria.

For the cases discussed so far, the SNSF expects that the applicants update their DMP before submitting its final version at the end of the project grant.

In contrast, Figure 4 presents the main reasons for requesting a revision of the DMP before the release of funds. This includes the following categories:

- The applicants envisage sharing their data on a website (personal webpage or webpage for a specific project), in the annex of the corresponding publication or in a data journal, for instance.
- The DMP lacks details regarding data sharing. There can be inconsistencies in the answers provided in the DMPs or it is unclear which part of the data can be shared or not.

Figure 3: Main reasons for conditional acceptance of a DMP (N=497)

- Data sharing will occur upon request, by contacting directly the applicant in order to gain access to the data (and not through a data repository), unless access is restricted for plausible reasons.
- The applicants ask for an embargo period before publishing the data.
- The applicants claim that their data cannot be shared, but they do not provide satisfactory explanations.
- No DMP was submitted although the project clearly generates data.

At the time of writing this report, all DMPs that had to be revised prior to the release of funds had been amended by the researchers and were subsequently accepted or accepted subject to conditions.

Figure 4: Main reasons for DMPs sent for revision (N=414)

4.4 Data Repositories

Among the 1,516 applications considered in this report, 831 (55%) mention at least one data repository, for a total of 146 different data repositories. This high number indicates that the landscape is diverse and that researchers have many options to deposit their data (e.g. general, discipline-specific or institutional data repositories). General repositories accept different file formats and/or data from all disciplines (e.g. Zenodo) while discipline-specific repositories accept mainly specific file formats (e.g. OpenNeuro) or data from a specific community (e.g. FORSbase). Institutional repositories are maintained by research performing institutions and serve mainly to store and share data of said institutions (e.g. ETH Research Collection or BORIS).

In this context, the analysis also shows that 210 DMPs refer to more than one data repository. While some researchers indicate different possibilities because they are still thinking about the most suitable data repository, others plan to deposit their data in different data repositories since they work with different data types (e.g. genomic data, imaging data, survey data, etc.).

Only repositories with the main purpose of data sharing were taken into account. Websites, collaboration platforms, platforms for scientific publications, data journals, data catalogues or data software, with some exceptions were not considered for the data analysis.

Which data repositories are widely considered among the applicants?

In total, researchers made 1,157 mentions of a specific data repository. Figure 5 presents the most cited data repositories in the DMPs for all disciplines, with at least five mentions each (N=1,157). A detailed analysis by main groups of disciplines - SSH, MINT and LS - is also presented. Finally, the figure indicates the type of each data repository (i.e. general, discipline-specific and institutional).

By considering all disciplines, we see that researchers primarily intend to use general repositories, most frequently citing Zenodo and Dryad, with 223 and 89 mentions respectively. While these data repositories are perfectly suited and comply with the FAIR Data Principles, the initial experiences of the SNSF Administrative Offices indicate that these general repositories were in certain cases mentioned because the researchers were not yet aware of field-specific solutions.

However, certain discipline-specific repositories are well known and used by the Swiss research community, for example FORSbase, GEO or SRA, with 68, 65 and 29 mentions, respectively. GitHub is also often indicated to deposit the code (65 mentions).

While the data on the aforementioned initiatives, except FORSbase, are shared through foreign or international entities, some researchers intend to deposit the data on their institutional repository, such as the ETH Research Collection or BORIS.

A similar pattern is discernible in the three main groups of disciplines, SSH, MINT and LS. In SSH, the discipline-specific repository FORSbase is the highest cited repository followed by the general repositories Zenodo and Harvard Dataverse. In MINT, Zenodo is the highest cited platform, followed by the institutional repository ETH Research Collection and the software development platform GitHub. In the LS, the general repositories Zenodo and Dryad are cited the most, followed by multiple platforms for genomic data (GEO, SRA, ENA, etc.) and the institutional repository ETH Research Collection. Some discipline-specific differences can be seen as well, as the platforms CCDC and EarthChem are only used in DMPs from the MINT field, whereas most of the platforms for genomic data are mentioned exclusively in the LS.

Finally, among the data repositories listed in Figure 5, two of them - GitHub and Figshare - have a commercial purpose and therefore applicants have to justify this choice in the DMP (e.g. data repository specific to a scientific community). These data repositories comply with the ORD requirements but the SNSF does not cover the related costs (see the article 2.13 in the General implementation regulations for the Funding Regulations).

How many data repositories comply with the FAIR Data Principles?

Around 70% of the data repositories suggested in the DMPs of funded applications comply with the SNSF criteria concerning the FAIR Data Principles¹. This percentage, however, is significantly higher when focusing on the most used data repositories. Almost all of the 35 data repositories listed in Figure 5 are considered as FAIR by the SNSF².

¹It should be pointed out that the SNSF was flexible in the application of its criteria at the stage of the data analysis and that some data repositories now meet the criteria, which was not the case when the DMPs were analyzed. Therefore, data about the *FAIRness* of data repositories should be interpreted in an indicative way.

²Yareta (formerly DLCM) and ERIC were in development during the assessment of the DMP. They comply now with the FAIR Data Principles. Petabyte Archive is still in development and its adherence to the FAIR Data Principles cannot be assessed.

Figure 5: Overview of data repositories mentioned in the DMPs of funded applications, with at least five occurrences

The main reasons why a data repository is not considered compliant with the SNSF requirements are the following:

- The data repository is not at maturity and still in development. It is therefore not possible to assess the FAIRness of the data repository;
- The data repository does not comply with one or more SNSF requirements concerning the FAIR Data principles. The absence of PID or long-term data preservation plan (e.g. data repository dependent on short-term project funding) are the two most problematic issues observed in the analysis of data repositories.

In any case, these aspects do not lead to a revision of the DMP, rather DMPs are conditionally accepted and the applicants are requested to clarify the situation of the data repository at the end of the project grant.

Data repositories: which countries are involved in the initiatives?

The registry of research data repositories re3data.org provides information about which countries run the data repositories. For the ones not listed in re3data, the repositories websites were consulted. Figure 6 shows the involvement of different countries for the 35 repositories that were mentioned at least five times (see also Figure 5). A repository was considered “multinational” if at least two countries contribute to the maintenance of the repository in either hosting data, providing funding, etc. As illustrated in Figure 6, most data repositories are supported by international initiatives, followed by data repositories managed by American and Swiss entities, respectively.

Figure 6: Country involvement in the most cited data repositories mentioned in the DMPs of funded applications (N=35)

5 Conclusion

This monitoring report focuses on the data sharing and management practices among the researchers having submitted an application to the SNSF since the introduction of the Open Research Data policy in October 2017. It provides an overview of the budgeted costs for granting access to research data, the DMP acceptance rate, and the data repositories mentioned by researchers.

In general, the results related to the DMPs are very encouraging. Many DMPs were very extensive and precise on the management of research data and a majority of them could be accepted without requesting a revision from the applicants. In addition, all the DMPs that were sent back for revision were improved by researchers and subsequently approved by the SNSF, such that the projects could be started without significant delays.

Only a small proportion of the applications considered in the report around 16% - budgeted costs for granting access to research data. By considering all 1,257 applications, which were approved by the

SNSF 2018, the total amount of requested ORD costs amounts to CHF 2 Mio. Compared with the total requested amount of CHF 989 Mio in 2018, the ORD costs account for 0.2% of the annual requested budget. Based on these first experiences, the eligible amount of CHF 10,000 for ORD costs generally seems appropriate. However, this percentage is only indicative and should be interpreted with caution due to the limitations explained under point 4.1. Additionally, in order to further strengthen the move towards more openness, more efforts are needed in order to reinforce education on this topic, to develop and to maintain data infrastructures and to ensure curation/preservation services. This concerns not only the SNSF but also other stakeholders and goes beyond the scope of this report.

Regarding the data repositories, many researchers intend to share their data on general repositories. This number might decrease over time, as researchers gain an increased awareness of the repository landscape and the further development of discipline-specific platforms. In parallel, researchers mentioned a large number and diversity of repositories in the DMPs. Additionally, many data repositories are still at an early stage of development and are not yet fully established in the respective scientific communities. This point supports the findings of von der Heyde (2019), who concludes that the high fragmentation of the data repository landscape should not be pushed further by developing new data repositories, rather the focus should be on consolidating and strengthening the existing ones. In this context, the SNSF plans to extend its recommendations of established data repositories that comply with the FAIR Data Principles on its ORD webpage, thereby making field-specific initiatives more visible.

Based on these predominantly positive experiences, the workshops organised since 2017 by different research institutions to discuss the SNSF requirements, as well as their direct support to researchers preparing a DMP, seem to have been helpful in increasing the knowledge about research data management practices. The SNSF made a continuous effort in this regard and participated in more than 30 workshops and presentations organised at Swiss research institutions on the subject of data sharing and data management since 2017. Additionally, the SNSF offers research communities the possibility of organising workshops and of discussing best practices in connection with open research data issues (e.g. how to best write a DMP, which data formats to employ, which repositories are most suitable, etc.) under the funding scheme “Scientific Exchanges”. However, this option has been used only sparsely by researchers. While the specific reasons for the low interest in this funding scheme are unclear, it is certainly important to keep on supporting initiatives and services in the future. In order to coordinate these various efforts, swissuniversities received in May 2019 a mandate from the State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) to elaborate a National Open Data Strategy.

6 Challenges and Perspectives

The topic of Open Research Data is evolving rapidly. While the SNSF considers the initial experiences since the implementation of the ORD policy to be positive, it will continue to monitor its implementation and effects. The SNSF is committed to continuing its participation in ORD discussions at a national and international level and to developing solutions with other stakeholders with regard to research data management, open research data and data repositories.

It is important to emphasise that the present report is based on researchers intentions as expressed in the submitted DMPs. In order to have a clearer picture of the actual data management and sharing practices of the researchers, the SNSF plans to conduct a follow-up analysis based on the output data provided by the applicants. This future analysis will make it possible to track ORD practices in more detail and to better assess the impact of the SNSF’s ORD policy and its corresponding implementation measures. Depending on the results and on the feedback received from the research communities, it will update its policy as appropriate. The SNSF recognises that data management practices are part of a learning process in which all involved stakeholders (scientists, research funding organisations, data repository managers, etc.) should play a role.

At the international level, Science Europe (SE) has recently set up a new Working Group “Data Sharing and Supporting Infrastructures” (DSSI). SE further has just published a collection of best-practice examples (Science Europe, 2020) based on the way member organisations support researchers with their data management responsibilities and on feedback from researchers about their experiences with DMPs (usefulness, challenges, etc.). As a member of Science Europe, the SNSF will contribute to discussions

at the international level and align itself with the international initiatives.

With regard to data repositories, as mentioned previously, the landscape is evolving rapidly. Many repositories that currently do not fulfil the FAIR data principles, might do so in the near future. Other funding agencies are increasingly integrating the FAIR Data Principles into their own data policies. However, the specific modes of implementation of the FAIR data principles still need clarification and are the focus of a report entitled “Turning FAIR into reality” by the European Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data. This is why the SNSF has, for now, elaborated its own assessment criteria for the data repositories, based on the FAIR Data principles. Some major challenges related to data repositories are the long term preservation of research data as well as questions related to data ownership and the reuse of data.

Finally, it should be stated that a DMP and data deposition are required by the SNSF in view of the end of a research project and the publications or other forms of output related to it. However, this will have implications on the data accumulation, processing and storage during the research process. Important issues are thus how to increase data literacy in the different research communities, how to strengthen the learning process on a wide scale and how to provide institutional support and infrastructure. It is therefore important to coordinate initiatives at the national level, especially with swissuniversities, and to define responsibilities among the different stakeholders in the area of data management and data infrastructures. This is the purpose of a mandate by the SERI to elaborate a national Open Research Data Strategy, given to swissuniversities. The SNSF is collaborating to this mandate.

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